

Family Bonding in Times of COVID-19

Aruna Jose CHF

Institute Mater Dei, Goa

Covid 19 pandemic has altered everyone’s lifestyle today. Families have been faced with the challenge of establishing a ‘new normal’ in their daily lives. The current pandemic has resulted in loss of predictability, loss of loved ones, loss of routine, loss of classroom learning, and loss of exposure to space. Therefore, we are homebound. The families have to ride through this challenge to regain this real bond of love and union among family members. It’s a new way of life for many families around the world but also an opportunity to strengthen familial bonds and enhance our relationship with God. It is not a loss or limitation with any kind of resentment but an invitation to rebuild our broken relationships in the families.

Digital Environment to Prayer Environment

Most families are affected by the digital environment which leads to loneliness, manipulation, exploitation, violence, the risk of addictions, isolations and gradual loss of contact within the family members (*Christus Vivit*, no. 88). But today family is called to be united in prayer in this growing fear of our vulnerable existence. The parents feel special need to inculcate in their children a desire for prayer, which was almost disappearing from families today. It is a time God has given to transmit to the children the Christian faith and the children emulate Christian faith through the good examples of their parents and grandparents. It is a time that children begin a journey of learning and deepening their faith. Highlighting this

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basic truth of Christian life Pope Francis says: “it is in the family that we first learn how to pray. There we come to know God, to grow into men and women of faith, and to see ourselves as members of God’s greater family, the Church” (*Message to Families*, 18 January 2015).

Individualism to Interdependency

It is commonly remarked that society in general and marriage in particular are growing more individualistic: “an excessive individualism that sees the family as, at best, a “way station, helpful when convenient... and easily swept aside when it proves inconvenient or tiresome” (*Amoris Laetitia*, Chap. 2). Individualism weakens family bonds and ends up in leaving each member of the family as an isolated unit, meaning, spouses are now ‘alone together.’ This fosters an attitude of constant suspicion, fear of commitment, self-centeredness and arrogance. This lockdown due to covid -19 invites couples to transcend human frailties and to overcome hurts and frustrations often created by years of misunderstanding and negativity. A sense of trust must be deepened and supported through the risk of leaning on each other and finding the other trustworthy. *Gaudium et Spes* reminds us, such an attempt to develop a relationship of trust can only be attained through “unflinching effort under the help of grace.” This moment of crisis enables the good communication between the spouses and helps to make family life more humane and can overcome ill-feelings towards each other.

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Regaining the Lost Love for the Elderly

Every Christian has a role to honor and care for the elderly. But the crude reality today is exactly the opposite; they are considered a burden in the family. Older people suffer not only by being deprived of human contact, but also from abandonment, loneliness and isolation. The time has come to begin working towards an effective change in attitude towards older people and to restore to them their rightful place in the family. As elderly parent faces the increasing loss of their freedoms, friends and identity and becomes more anxious and dependent, we need to let go of anything in our parent's journey that does not belong to us. We should tell our children that older people represent the "historical memory" of the younger generations. They are the bearers of fundamental human values. Where this memory is lacking, people are rootless; they lack any capacity to project themselves with hope towards a future that transcends the limits of the present. The family will benefit greatly from a reevaluation of the educational role of older people. Pope Francis said that grandparents were "the indispensable link in educating children and young people in the faith" (*Address*, 21 January 2020).

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Youth Return to Home Space

The outbreak of corona-virus and the social distancing have affected the youth to stressful situations; no gatherings around, no dating possibilities, no entertainments etc. It is a U-turn from web space to home space. In this context, the message of Pope Francis to the youth is appropriate: "Open wide the doors of your life! May your time and space be filled with meaningful relationships, real people with whom to share your authentic and concrete experiences of daily life" (22 Feb 2018). It is a time to renew their faith they received from home; to revive the wise instructions of their parents; to give

due respect to their parents and grandparents and to give space to their brothers and sisters. The book of Proverbs teaches: "Hear, my child, your father's instruction, and do not reject your mother's teaching; for they are a fair garland for your head and pendants for your neck" (1: 8-9).

Conclusion: Community Service/Social Activism

Since the outbreak of the novel coronavirus, God provided us with ample opportunities to think beyond ourselves and more about our family as a whole. No family drops down from heaven perfectly formed; families need constantly to grow and mature in the ability to love. The life of every family is marked by all kinds of crisis, yet they are part of life: each problem or calamity whether manmade or natural, has a lesson to teach which will lead to a spirituality that upholds the family. In order to have a healthy family life, Pope Francis asks us to practice three words: *Please, Thank you and Sorry*. Covid-19 is a God-given opportunity and let's pledge to heed to the call of our Holy Father to exercise above three essential words as they are the key to living well and in peace both inside and outside our home (*General Audience*, World meeting of Families, 21-26 August 2018).